

Measurements and Sensitivities of Neutron Leakage from the PARADIGM Integral Experiment

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ABSTRACT

Integral benchmark experiments are essential for the adjustment and validation of nuclear data (ND). Considering multiple integral responses in ND adjustment has been previously shown to strongly reduce ND uncertainties. Therefore, this work aims to provide neutron leakage measurements and sensitivities from the PARADIGM integral experiment to be used as an additional metric, apart from the neutron multiplication factor, k_{eff} , to reduce ND uncertainties in the 1–600 keV range. Neutron leakage measurements have been conducted for two fast Pu-metal assemblies using a set of Bonner sphere spectrometers. These measurements are simulated in the Monte Carlo N-Particle (MCNP) transport code using multiple ND libraries and compared to measured results. Preliminary energy-binned sensitivities limited to the $^{239}\text{Pu}(n, \text{fission})$ reaction are calculated using the novel MCNP fixed-source sensitivity tool, and via the manual perturbation of ND. Simulation-measurement comparison reveals differences in the peak position of the BSS response distribution when different ND libraries are used. This indicates variation in the simulation of the mean energy of neutron flux due to inconsistencies in ND. Preliminary sensitivity results show good agreement between sensitivities calculated with the MCNP fixed-source sensitivity tool and the manual-perturbation approach. The results of both approaches indicate that the neutron leakage is an extremely sensitive response, with sensitivities greater than 1. The observation of sensitivities greater than 1 will not be seen for k_{eff} , therefore, leakage spectra will serve as a meaningful quantity for the adjustment of ND in the 1-600 keV range.

Keywords: Nuclear Data, Neutron Leakage, Sensitivities, Fast Neutron Detection

1. INTRODUCTION

The accuracy of a model for nuclear applications is fundamentally constrained by the quality of the nuclear data (ND) on which it relies. The validation and adjustment of ND is heavily reliant upon integral experiments. These experiments are used to assess the accuracy of ND in the modeling of critical and subcritical arrangements of special nuclear material. However, measurements of integral experiments providing only the effective neutron multiplication factor, k_{eff} , have been shown to have limited impact on the understanding of ND [1] due to the effects of compensating error [2, 3]. Previous work [1, 2, 4] has demonstrated that the simultaneous adjustment of ND with reference to multiple integral quantities results in greater reduction of ND uncertainty than when only k_{eff} is used. As part of the Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) PARAllel Approach of Differential and InteGral Measurements (PARADIGM) Laboratory Directed Research and Development (LDRD) project, this work seeks to provide calculated neutron leakage sensitivities in addition to experimental and simulated neutron leakage measurements for the adjustment of nuclear data. This adjustment will be done with the generalized least squares (GLS) and iteratively reweighted least squares (IRLS) methods described in [1], to adjust nuclear data to the integral measurements, with consideration of covariances and sensitivities, to produce nuclear data and associated uncertainties with improved accuracy.

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2. THEORY

2.1. Sensitivities

A sensitivity is a measure of the degree to which a change in an input parameter affects a corresponding change in a system output. In the context of ND, a sensitivity is the relative change of a response due to the change in a ND quantity such as a cross section. The first order sensitivity coefficient, $S_{(R,x)}$, describing the change of a response, R , to some ND quantity of interest, x , is quantitatively defined in equation (1):

$$S_{(R,x)} = \frac{x}{R_0} \frac{\partial R}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

The magnitude of a sensitivity is important when considering the accuracy of ND used for a simulation. Large sensitivities are highly correlated/anti-correlated to the simulation of interest. Therefore, when simulation-measurement bias is present, ND with high sensitivities to the response of interest should be investigated first as the possible source of the bias. Sensitivities can be further exploited to understand ND uncertainties when the sensitivity vectors are combined with ND covariance. By identifying which ND quantities have high sensitivities and/or significant uncertainties, specific ND improvements can be prioritized to reduce simulation bias. Multiple methods exist for calculating sensitivities, two of which are explored in this work.

2.1.1. MCNP fixed-source sensitivity tool (FSEN)

As part of the Experiments Underpinned by Computational Learning for Improvements in Nuclear Data (EUCLID) project [2], a new tool for the Monte Carlo N-Particle (MCNP) transport code [5] was developed to directly calculate ND sensitivities of tallied responses in fixed-source simulations [6]. This novel tool, FSEN, uses adjoint weighting to calculate ND sensitivities via the combination of the forward and adjoint transport equations and perturbation theory, used to obtain equation (2) [7]:

$$S_{(R,x)} = \frac{\langle f_{R,x}, \Psi \rangle + \langle \Psi^\dagger, Q_x \rangle - \langle \Psi^\dagger, H_x \rangle}{R}, \quad (2)$$

where $f_{(R,x)}$ is the portion of the response dependent on the ND (x), Q_x is the portion of the source term impacted by the ND, H_x is the portion of a given transport operator (collision, scattering, and fission) dependent on the ND, and Ψ^\dagger is the adjoint angular flux. The angular brackets in equation (2) indicate integration over all phase space, evaluated via the FSEN card in MCNP [7]. For this work, simulations were run with a development version of MCNP6 which includes the FSEN feature. Currently, the FSEN feature does not support parallel execution using MPI. To achieve high statistics, 10 different MCNP simulations with unique random number seeds were ran on separate nodes, with the final sensitivity and uncertainty values taken as the mean and standard deviation of the independent simulation results.

2.1.2. Manual perturbation of nuclear data files

The second approach for neutron leakage sensitivity calculation is via the direct perturbation of ND used for simulations. This method is well established, included in the MCNP PERT card [8]. However, the PERT card is limited to perturbations of density, composition, or cross section, and cannot be used for other ND quantities. To assess sensitivities to various ND quantities, ND files are therefore perturbed directly. This approach has been successfully implemented in recent work [9]. This method relies upon the central difference approximation of the first order derivative, obtained via the Taylor series expansion. This approximation enables equation (1) to be expressed as equation (3) [9],

$$S_{(R,x)} \approx \frac{x_+ - x_-}{2x_0 p}, \quad (3)$$

where x_0 is the response of interest simulated with unperturbed data, x_+ is the simulated response using positively perturbed ND, x_- is the simulated response using negatively perturbed ND, and p is the fractional perturbation amount, describing the percentage by which the cross section is changed. The uncertainty of the sensitivity, $\sigma_{S_{R,x}}$, is propagated from the statistical uncertainty of the simulated responses, described in equation (4), where σ_{x_0} , σ_{x_+} , and σ_{x_-} are the statistical uncertainties for the unperturbed, positively perturbed, and negatively perturbed simulation results respectively.

$$\sigma_{S_{R,x}}^2 = \left(\frac{\delta S}{\delta x_0} \right)^2 \sigma_{x_0}^2 + \left(\frac{\delta S}{\delta x_+} \right)^2 \sigma_{x_+}^2 + \left(\frac{\delta S}{\delta x_-} \right)^2 \sigma_{x_-}^2 \quad (4)$$

For the central difference approximation to be valid, it is assumed that the Taylor series expansion may be truncated at the linear term. If the perturbation size is too large, the response will change drastically, resulting in a central difference approximation that reflects the response nonlinearities, making the first-order Taylor series expansion inaccurate. However, if the perturbation size is too small, the difference in calculated responses will be smaller than the simulation statistical error [7]. To quantify the linearity of the response, the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) is used to measure the linear correlation between the perturbation size, and the response change, expressed as in equation (5), where x_i is the magnitude of fractional perturbation, and y_i is the response. The optimal perturbation size is that which results in a change in response greater than the uncertainty, for which the PCC is closest to 1. Perturbation size optimization is required for each response to ensure validity of the method.

$$PCC = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (5)$$

3. METHODS

3.1. The PARADIGM Assembly

The PARADIGM assembly was designed to target neutron energies of 1–600 keV, as this range encompasses the unresolved resonance region in which ^{239}Pu ND for several reactions are poorly characterized [1]. The full energy range is divided into two experiments, the first targets neutron energies between 30–600 keV, using only interstitial trays of alumina as a neutron moderator. The second has alumina and graphite plates in addition to the alumina trays, targeting the 1–30 keV range (Figure 1). Aside from the interstitial material, the other major components of the assemblies are the same between the two configurations, both using the Zero Power Physics Reactor (ZPPR) Plutonium Aluminum No-Nickle (PANN) fuel plates [10], a copper reflector, and both assembled on the Comet vertical lift assembly [11]. The ZPPR plates are assembled into alumina trays, which are stacked with interstitial moderation layers inside the copper reflector. A complete fuel layer consists of 40 ZPPR plates in the alumina tray.

For the neutron leakage measurements, a slightly subcritical state was required to avoid overwhelming the detectors. Due to the difference in moderation between the two assemblies, a different number of fuel plates were required to achieve the desired condition for each experimental configuration. When fully assembled for the neutron leakage measurements, configuration 1 consisted of 5 fuel layers on the upper fixed platform of the Comet vertical lift assembly, and 3 fuel layers on the lower moveable platen. Configuration 2 consisted of 8 fuel layers on the upper platform, and 7 layers on the lower. A summary of the moderating material, target energy range, and number of fuel plates used for each configuration during the neutron leakage measurements are presented in Table I.

Figure 1. Photos show PARADIGM Experiment Configuration 1 (a) and Configuration 2 (b). assembled on the Comet vertical lift assembly.

Table I. Features of Experimental Configurations used for BSS Measurements.

Configuration	Target Energy Range	Moderator	Number of Fuel Plates
1	30-600 keV	Alumina	320
2	1-30 keV	Alumina and Graphite	590

For the manual perturbation sensitivity calculation method, the simulated system must remain in a subcritical state even when the cross sections are perturbed. Therefore to maintain a subcritical state, the separation of the assembly halves is increased from 0.07" to 1" in the simulation model. Increase in the separation does not change the neutron leakage spectra distribution, only the flux magnitude.

3.2. Neutron Detectors

A set of Bonner Sphere Spectrometers (BSS) from ELSE NUCLEAR [12] were used for these measurements, comprising of one spherical ^3He detector and six polyethylene spheres with varying outer diameters of 3", 4", 5", 6", 8" and 10". The ^3He detector has a diameter of 1.3", with a fill gas of 2.3 atm of ^3He and 1.2 atm Kr. When assembled, the ^3He detector is placed at the center of each polyethylene sphere. Due to the competing effects of neutron absorption and moderation in the polyethylene, the number of detection events for an incident neutron spectrum varies as a function of polyethylene thickness such that each detector is sensitive to a different range of incident neutron energies. In a discretized form, the count rate measured from a particular sphere, C_i is described by equation (6),

$$C_i = \sum_{j=1}^N R_{ij} \phi_j \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M, \quad (6)$$

where C_i is dependent on the neutron flux in the j^{th} energy group, ϕ_j , and the response function, R_{ij} of

the i^{th} sphere averaged over energy group j . The response function to the, R_{ij} , is related to the thickness of the polyethylene surrounding the detector; BSS with little or no moderation are sensitive to thermal neutrons, while BSS with more moderating material are sensitive to fast neutrons.

3.2.1. Experimental Setup

For both PARADIGM configurations, the BSS lifted such that each detector active volume is centered at the assembly mid-height (see Figure 2), and approximately 70" from the copper reflector. Two measurements are conducted for each BSS: one with a 4" thick polyethylene shield placed between the BSS and the assembly, and one unshielded. The shielded measurement isolates the scattered neutron contribution to the response so that it may be subtracted from the unshielded measurement to achieve the detector response to neutrons from the assembly without room return. Each sphere is sequentially exposed to both assemblies, with the two assembly halves separated between measurements to allow for the lowering/raising of the shield, and the replacement of the BSS with a different diameter sphere.

Figure 2. The photo (a) shows the arrangement of the polyethylene shielded measurement of Configuration 2 with 10" BSS. The photo (b) shows the same measurement as pictured in (a) but for the unshielded case.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Measurement-Simulation Comparison

The BSS measurements were conducted at a slightly subcritical state. As a result, the k_{eff} uncertainty bounds multiplications ranging from subcritical to critical. Absolute magnitude comparison of the BSS response between simulation and measurement is therefore not possible. Instead, a normalized response has been presented for simulation and measurement results for configuration 1 and 2 in Figures 4 and 3 respectively. Two ND libraries, ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1, are used for the simulations. To isolate the effects of individual ND between the two libraries, targeted simulations were performed. This was done for Plutonium and Copper data. For each case, all isotopes of Cu or Pu were modeled with ENDF/B-VIII.1, while all other materials were modeled with ENDF/B-VIII.0. This procedure was conducted separately for Cu and Pu to evaluate their individual contributions to the response.

Variation of the ND libraries is demonstrated to result in a notable response difference. This is most evident for the shielded case of configuration 2 shown in Figure 3. Both ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 result in a shift of the peak position to higher diameter BSS compared to the measured response,

Figure 3. Configuration 2 measurement-simulation comparison for unshielded and shielded cases with multiple ND libraries. Results demonstrate shift in peak response position with ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 compared to measurement for both shielded and unshielded cases.

Figure 4. Configuration 1 measurement-simulation comparison for unshielded and shielded cases with multiple ND libraries. Results demonstrate shift in peak response position with ENDF/B-VIII.0. and ENDF/B-VIII.1 compared to measurement for the unshielded case, while the shielded case demonstrates good matching.

indicating that both libraries overestimate the mean energy of the neutron leakage. The inverse is seen for the unshielded case, where the peak position is shifted to a lower diameter for ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1. For both cases, the peak position is matched when Plutonium and Copper data alone are changed to ENDF/B-VIII.1. These results are reflected for the unshielded case of configuration 1, shown in Figure 4, which shows the same overestimation in the mean neutron leakage energy. Configuration 1 differs for the shielded case, achieving agreement in distribution shape for all ND variations. It is also notable that all cases of configurations 1 and 2 underestimate the contribution of the bare (0") BSS in the simulation. This is due to deficiencies in the room model used for the simulation, resulting in an underestimation of scattered neutrons and a subsequent underestimation of the bare BSS response.

Energy-binned sensitivities for the 5" BSS response for the unshielded case of configuration 2 are shown in Figure 5. These are calculated for the $^{239}\text{Pu}(n, \text{fission})$ cross section with both FSEN and manual perturbation methods. Good agreement between the results of the FSEN and manual perturbation methods can be seen, with overall similarity in the distribution shape and peak locations. A reduction in uncertainty would benefit the assessment of agreement in sensitivity magnitude between methods. The

dominant contributor to uncertainty in both methods is simulation statistics, which could be reduced with longer computing times or variance reduction techniques.

The observation of sensitivities greater than unity is significant, as sensitivities of this magnitude will not be seen for k_{eff} . The k_{eff} value is limited to a much smaller scale, for critical systems this is bound about the value 1. As a result, the magnitude of the response change possible with the perturbation of nuclear data is small. Neutron leakage is not bound to the same scale. Very small perturbations in cross section can result in many orders of magnitude increase to flux production. As a result, for cross sections that are strongly coupled to the neutron population such as fission, capture, and $\bar{\nu}$, we should expect to see very large sensitivities that exceed 1, as has been demonstrated for the results of the ^{239}Pu total fission cross section sensitivity.

Figure 5. Sensitivities calculated for 5" BSS response to the $^{239}\text{Pu}(n, \text{fission})$ cross section for the unshielded case of PARADIGM configuration 2 calculated by the FSEN tool and manual perturbation methods. Results indicate good matching between methods, validating the novel FSEN tool.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Neutron leakage measurements were successfully conducted within the 1–600 keV range with BSS. Comparisons between simulated and measured results using multiple ND libraries show discrepancies in the peak position of the response, indicating inaccuracies in the mean neutron leakage energy simulated for both configurations. This was seen for both ENDF/B-VIII.1 and ENDF/B-VIII.0, with matching achieved for only ENDF/B-VIII.1 Plutonium and Copper data. Preliminary sensitivities were presented for one reaction, the $^{239}\text{Pu}(n, \text{fission})$ cross section, calculated via two methods. These calculated sensitivities show good agreement between methods, and indicate that neutron leakage is an extremely sensitive parameter that will be impactful for ND adjustment. This work is ongoing and will be expanded upon to include sensitivities to both configurations for the full set of BSS and multiple reactions. A reduction of uncertainty in the FSEN and manual-perturbation calculated sensitivities is also required for improved comparison of the methods. The end goal of this work is to provide sensitivity data in addition to measured and simulated responses for the reduction of ^{239}Pu ND uncertainty in the 1–600 keV range.

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